

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Dog Soap by Using Natural Ingredients to Control the Deer Tick *Ixodes scapularis*

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Ticks and fleas are the banes of any dog's life. These pesky parasites increase manifold during the warmer months and are a cause of stress for every dog owner. Ticks are voracious blood suckers and cause inflammation, irritation, and excessive scratching in dogs. Though there are many medications in pet shops that can treat fleas effectively, some of them can be harsh on dogs. The most common sign associated with tick infestation is pruritus, which is present in 100% of the cases. So, we don't have to expose our dog to toxic tick medication because we're going to share some tried and tested natural tick treatment soaps that are safe for our dog and the owner too. In many places in Nagaon district, many people use some plant-based medicine to treat ticks, but we have made it as a dog soap using natural ingredients that are scientifically useful and excellent and made it available for use so that people can easily make it at home. This soap is effective in treating those wounds caused by the bites of *Ixodes scapularis*, and it will make the coat of our pooch healthier and clearer. Customise this recipe to meet 4-legged's fur and skin needs using *Azadirachta indica* as our soap base and white vinegar for antibacterial and deodorant properties, and add aloe vera gel for hydrating, skin-soothing support. The paper tries to produce the traditional process of making homemade disinfectant dog soap to fit any need, any budget, and whatever time we have available.

Keywords: Natural, dog soap, effective, homemade, *Ixodes scapularis*